

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON THE CHARACTERS DEVELOPMENT IN "BUD NOT BUDDY" AND "A BOY WITH FIVE CHILDREN"

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ABSTRACT

This article compares the personality traits and character development of orphan heroes covered in American and Uzbek literature. Emphasis is placed on the creative achievements of the writers of the two nations, focusing on how the development of the characters is revealed in the content of the works.

Background. The image of an orphan is one of the most impressive images that cannot be ignored by children and adults. Depicting "orphan heroes" in children's literature and revealing their character traits can only be done by skilled writers/ Childrens' favourite authors Khudoyberdi Tokhtabaev in Uzbek literature and Christopher Paul Curtis in American literature describe children's characters so skillfully that the reader becomes like close friends who have known the main characters for many years. By comparing these images, we not only discover the relationship between the historical period, national life, individual genres and writing styles in the literature of two nations, but also learn human virtues, to be invincible, hardworking, ambitious in life.

Methods. In this article, the methods of analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, analogy are effectively used in the comparative analysis of the "orphan" characters development in American and Uzbek children's literature.

Results. The results show that in the depiction of "orphans" in the literature of two genetically unrelated nations, there are some similarities in the development of the characters, but the differences in social and political situations affect the character traits of the characters.

Conclusion. Despite the fact that the discussed works of American and Uzbek literature reflect the lives of children in different parts of the world, the psychology, feelings, experiences, and characteristics of orphans form a commonality. Even the things that worry the protagonists or make them happy, anger them or soften their hearts are the same. The children's story in American literature also share some exact resemblance with the novel in Uzbek literature in the choice the images that oppress or support the main heroes.

Introduction. Any fictional work must depict realistic character development with a compelling character arc in order to

mirror real life. These characters also need to have convincing personality features that develop as the character does. As adults can have a skewed perception of how children think and feel, this is one of the main obstacles of developing characters for children's books. However, children's favorite Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev and inspiring American author of young people's literature Christopher Paul Curtis showed their extraordinary talent in their books – "A boy with five children" and "Bud, not Buddy". Both main protagonists of these books feel real and stand out from the rest with their amazing personality traits.

Although there is no national and historical closeness in American and Uzbek literature, there are artistic elements that serve as a basis for comparative analysis. There are many works in which the symbol of "orphan" is embodied in the children's literature of the two nations. However, there are rarely realistic works that cover social issues, such as Christopher Paul Curtis's "Bud, not Buddy" and Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboev's "A boy with five children". Comparing the development of the characters in them allows us to identify the similarities and differences, achievements and shortcomings of the writers of the two nations.

Methods. The methods of analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction and analogy were effectively used in the comparative analysis of the development of "orphan" characters in American and Uzbek children's literature to carry out the research for the article

In this article, the manual and scientific works were used during the research including "Understanding Children's Literature" by Peter Hunt, "Bud, Not Buddy

Study Guide" by Abby Federico, "A Navigator, a novel study guide for "Bud, not buddy" by Christopher Paul Curtis" by William and Mary, "Artistic psychology in the novels of Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboev" by Rukhsora Tulabaeva.

Discussion. There are a lot of young orphans whose father has passed away and who have lost their mother. Those little orphans always hope that their father would come back, but they lack the courage to go looking for them. A small kid who is tired of moving from house to house is the subject of the inspirational and entertaining novel Bud not Buddy. He lost his mother, but thanks to a little briefcase he carries around, he still has hope for his father. Christopher Curtis uses little details to portray his characters, even though that they are barely mentioned in the novel.

Amoses, who have a son that is two years older than Bud, have adopted Bud and are hosting him in their home. Todd, Amoses' only child, teases Bud because he doesn't like having a new boy in his home. Todd and Bud got into a quarrel and Mrs. Amoses saw it. She took Todd's suitcase and threw him into the shed. Bud quickly makes his way out of the shed in pursuit of his possessions. However, even before he discovered them: "I could tell right away that someone had been fumbling through my things. First off, whenever I put the blanket in, I always fold it so that it stops all the other things from banging up against each other", Bud is extremely careful about where things are placed in his briefcase.

This demonstrates that he is perceptive and careful with the things he values. He thinks, everything should have its own place, and he is aware whenever something isn't working the way he intended it to. Someone must care deeply about

something if they're aware of every detail. Bud clearly values the items in the suitcase since he follows a specific order in which they must be placed: "first, whenever I put the blanket in, I always fold it so it stops...things from banging." This demonstrates the great care Bud takes with the suitcase. It's vital to him, thus he doesn't want anything to clash and cause damage.

Although Bud presents himself as a polite well-mannered youngster, he is actually trying to find a way out of a sticky situation. He invents so many rules for the lies he invents that he names them: Bud Caldwell's Rules and Things to Have a Funner Life and Make a Better Liar of Yourself.

Once Todd has assaulted him, and when Mrs. Amoses enters, Todd lies to his mother to get him out of trouble. Bud is taken aback when Todd appears to know how to comply with his instructions in order to avoid problems. He appeared to understand some of the same concepts as me, which I constantly consider and strive to remember in order to avoid making the same mistakes. "It seemed like he knew some of the same things I know, the things I think of all the time and try to remember so I don't make the same mistake more than seven or eight times". This demonstrates that Bud is intelligent and a quick learner, since he actively seeks out information on how to win over others. He simply needs something to occur "seven or eight times" before he decides whether or not to lie as a result of that knowledge. Bud even refers to himself as one of the world's best liars. You must learn when to utilize a skill in order to be the greatest at it. Bud had to practice using it when appropriate, demonstrating that he is also capable of

being conceited and egotistical. He is therefore shocked when he discovers that others are able to use the same technique. In Bud's words, he's "on the lame" after leaving the Amoses' home. He glances through his baggage before he can take any more action. A photograph of his mother as a young girl is in his bag. He remembers a talk he and his mother used to constantly have when he looks at this photo. "Bud is your name and don't you ever let anyone call you anything outside of that either...Especially don't you ever let anyone call you Buddy, I may have some problems but being stupid isn't one of them, I would've added that dy onto the end of your name if I intended for it to be there." She would have placed it there if she had intended something to occur or be there. Additionally, Bud's obedience is demonstrated by the fact that he consistently introduces himself as Bud rather than Buddy. Because his mother didn't want to be called Buddy, he is particularly refusing to allow anybody do so.

Bud tries to be as polite, but it seems like very few people actually notice. Herman C. Calloway is one of them. To discover the man Bud believes to be his father, Bud has traveled a long way. He knows where Mr. Calloway could be and keeps a flyer of him in his bag. After spending a few days with Mr. Calloway, Bud has finally reached his breaking point. "You throw a lot of 'sirs' around but you've still got a real strong, real smart-mouthed, disrespectful streak in you boy." he says. Nobody else notices Bud's "disrespectful streak," but Mr. Calloways does.

A young, motivated orphan who is only seeking to find his father but who has also experienced a lot to get there is shown

throughout the entire novel. On the Barnes and Nobles website, a parent wrote: "Bud he's an adventurous boy. He's brave. He's strong. He's determined to do anything. He's determined to find his father. Read this book and you'll find out how he goes from adventure to adventure. From foster home to foster home. Feel as if you're Bud as you read the book. And enjoy it." This review does an excellent job of breaking down Bud's personality since he is brave and searched for his father despite not knowing what he would encounter. He shown strength by finding a solution on his own after he was parted from his companion. He is resolute since nothing stood in his way of reaching his goal.

Arifjon is the main protagonist of the book about the period of suffering and struggles. He is a cheerful, innocent, faithful, conscientious, fair, naive young boy by nature, but the war period and the difficulties of life make him a more tenacious, responsible, determined person who thinks like an adult, sometimes even makes him a liar and leads him to the wrong path in life. The author does not just write, but make you feel it. While reading Arifjon's story, readers sometimes smile inadvertently or burst out laughing, sometimes admire his courage, hard work, and enthusiasm, and sometimes they are disgusted by the unscrupulous people who hurt him. As the story is narrated by the main character, the description of his thoughts allows the reader to easily understand the character of Arifjon. For example, let us look at these extracts:

"Now I can't play at all, if I get addicted to the game, all my work at home will be left behind. Then my mother may be upset. I love my mother, I love her very, very much. My mother also loves me: "Thankfully, I

gave birth to you when I was young and naive, otherwise, what would happen to me?" ...

I purposely give Zulaiha less work, because girls are fragile, and as they are fragile, they should be taken care of.

...I think my brother Osman is very dreamy, sometimes he falls asleep in front of the stove while cooking. Moreover, he is so thin that he is like a kosova that puts fire in the tandoor. He paints all day, and his is getting quite good at it. We all have high hopes for him. We think he will be a great artist. That's why I don't order him to do anything. I think that if he has a lot of free time, he will draw a lot, and if he draws a lot, he will mature faster...

...We are sitting here cooking sumak, playing donkey midi, watching dances, what about my father, where is he now? Maybe he's sitting in a cold trench thinking. Or maybe they attacked with a machine gun, or he could not find someone to read the letter from us and crawled from trench to trench...

Oh my dad, my daddy..."

From the extracts, one can be impressed by his kindness, care and love for his family. But Arifjon is not depicted only with positive manners, sometimes he is mischevious, sometimes weak, sometimes he cannot do anything to help his siblings. Difficult times prompted him to sin in order to do good to his loved ones:

"... So what, can a person become a thief by stealing just one melon? I would never do it to myself, but I feel sorry for my sick sister..."

These qualities make him realistic. Real characters are easier to empathize with and therefore the story is likeable and enjoyable to read about. As you see Arifhan's personal traits are revealed

through his own inner voice, and sometimes through the conversations he has with other characters. Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboev did not use any additional definitions and explanations nor justify the main protagonist, but he let the reader to make his own judgement.

Although he is only 13 years old, Arifjon is very responsible like an adult. After his father goes to war, he is buried with household chores. And the death of his mother seems to push the orphans into the abyss. Arifjon becomes a mother and father to five orphans in his teenage years.

In the course of the story, Arifjon grows up as a hard-working, conscientious, responsible person, because of his honesty and courage, he exposed the crime in the orphanage. No matter how hard life challenges him, he does not lose his pride and identity. Arifjon, who wants to buy grapes to cheer up his sick sister, wants to earn money by telling anecdotes. But after hearing the anecdote, the passenger, who is greedy desoite being rich, threw five pennies to him. This hurts the orphan boy's pride and he throws the coin at the passenger:

...I don't need your charity, you know I won't get it even if I die. A sigh came from inside of me, no, I pulled it together, I did not cry...

He is not only proud, but also intelligent. His intelligence can be seen in different places in the story: when he thinks up tactics in the battle for the hill, when he gets an excellent grade from the subject mother tongue, when he punishes the duty officer who was sleeping in the police station, when he walks the road from Tashkent to Kokhan with his siblings and overcomes the obstacles they encounter on the way.

Results. While comparing two children's books about orphan boys, it can be noticed that both Christopher Curtis and Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev used multiple aspects to improve his characters. Aspects like symbolism, flashbacks, foreshadowing, irony most importantly are employed in character development. They make you feel the emotions that Bud and Arifjon feel. Bud is the boy who is obedient but also disrespectful in his own way while Arifjon is helpless but proud, very young but responsible boy. Christopher Curtis used fleshbacks and foreshadowing effectively to develop his characters. Not only does he give you a view of the characters living in the book but also the one who isn't, Bud's mother, Angela Caldwell or Calloway. Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev embodied his character by his inner voice and give readers a chance to judge the characters themselves.

Conclusion. The development of heroes is perfectly described in the works of two great writers of American and Uzbek children's literature, featuring the image of an orphan. Although some characteristic traits of the main heroes, their dreams and goals are similar, the creators used different approaches to revealing them. Christopher Paul describes the character of the hero more with his inner experiences built on the basis of memories. He uses slang and street words in the characters' language to make him appear more realistic. This method was also used by Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboyev, it is not difficult to notice the national identity, simplicity and children's language in Orifjon's anecdotes. But in the works of the Uzbek writer, the development of the hero is revealed through the inner feelings of the character in different situations, through

his dialogue with himself. All in all, the orphan images created by two children's favorite writers could become close friends of book lovers. If the characters had not been properly developed, the novels would

not have had enough excitement and adventure to leave the reader with the everlasting feeling that they can do what they set their mind to.

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